

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt(II) as Mixed Chelate Complex with *p*-Nitrobenzoylacetylacetanilide and Sulphocyanide

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Cobalt(II) has been determined by extracting with *p*-nitrobenzoylacetylacetanilide in presence of ammonium sulphocyanide into isobutylmethylketone and measuring the absorbance at 625 nm against solvent blank. Thus, 3 to 50 μg of cobalt has been determined with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.92\%$. The extracting pH of 3 to 4 is maintained by KCl-HCl buffer. The determination is possible in the presence of 37 metal ions commonly associated with cobalt in ores and alloys. Thus, not only the selectivity of the reaction is high, but also the sensitivity, 0.03 ppm, is appreciable.

SEVERAL β -keto compounds like benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide¹ and *o*-mercapto acetoacetanilide² have been reported as analytical reagent for cobalt though the complexes are not very strong. In this investigation, *p*-nitrobenzoyl acetanilide, a newly introduced reagent, has been used for extraction of cobalt(II) quantitatively in the presence of thiocyanate into isobutyl-methyl ketone and its spectrophotometric estimation in presence of 37 other metal ions.

Experimental

Procedure for preparation of *p*-nitrobenzoyl acetanilide: *p*-Nitrobenzoyl ethyl acetate was synthesised following the method for the synthesis of benzoyl ethylacetate³ using *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride in place of benzoyl chloride. However, the experimental conditions were modified as described here. The solid ester was taken in xylene and refluxed with aniline at 160° on an oil bath for 6 hr under an air condenser. The reaction mixture was finally chilled (5°) and petroleum ether (40-60°) was added to separate the anilide with manual stirring. The product was crystallised from aqueous acetone. The compound melted at 160-161°. *p*-Nitrobenzoyl chloride was in turn prepared following a standard method⁴ from *p*-nitrobenzoic acid and thionyl chloride.

Reagents and apparatus: A 4% (0.14 M) solution of *p*-nitrobenzoylacetylacetanilides in aqueous ethanol (30%) was used. A stock solution of cobalt sulphate (AR, BDH) (10^{-3} M) in dil. H_2SO_4 was prepared and standardised. At lower pH, KCl-HCl buffer and at higher pH, potassium phthalate-HCl buffer were used. Absorbance was recorded on a Beckman DB, Model 26 spectrophotometer.

Procedure for cobalt(II): To an aliquot of the standard cobalt(II) solution containing 5-50 μg of the metal, 1 g of ammonium thiocyanate and 1 ml

of the reagent solution were added. The mixture was diluted with water and KCl-HCl buffer so that the final volume was 20 ml and the pH was 2.0. The cobalt complex was extracted with two 5 ml batches of isobutyl methyl ketone. The two organic layers were mixed, dehydrated with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance of the green extract was measured at 625 nm using pure solvent as blank.

This procedure was applied to the determination of cobalt in monel metal (0.5 g) or nickel ore (0.5-1 g), decomposed and diluted to 1 litre and 10 litres, respectively. An aliquot of 3 to 4 ml was taken.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curve: The absorbance values of several extracts of cobalt(II) with varying metal ion concentration were recorded over the full range (570-670 nm) using the reagent blank. The curve indicated that the λ_{max} was at 625 nm. Similar curve for the reagent solution against solvent blank showed that the λ_{max} for the reagent was at 390 nm and it had negligible absorbance above 460 nm. Therefore, solvent blank was used in further determination of cobalt.

Effect of thiocyanate: It has been already mentioned that the colour was developed and extracted only in presence of thiocyanate. Under the conditions of the experiments the addition of 1 g of ammonium thiocyanate was sufficient.

Effect of pH: A set of cobalt(II) solutions adjusted to different pH values with suitable buffers were extracted in isobutyl methyl ketone and the absorbance was measured. A KCl-HCl buffer was used for lower pH values and potassium phthalate-HCl buffer for pH values 3 to 4. Acetate buffer was used for even higher pH values. It was observed

that the range of pH for complete extraction was 1 to 4.

Effect of reagent concentration : 0.5 mg reagent was necessary and sufficient for the range of the concentration of cobalt (5-50 μg) determined, while five-fold excess of the reagent had no adverse effect.

Extracting solvent : Extraction was rapid and quantitative (99.5% in one step) in isobutyl methyl ketone, slow and quantitative in chloroform but incomplete in other common solvents tried, restricting the choice to iso-butyl methyl ketone.

Stability of colour : Absorbance values of several extracts containing different amounts of cobalt were measured at intervals of 30 min after extraction. The colour was found to be stable up to 3 hr.

Optimum concentration range and absorptivity : On plotting the absorbance values of the extracts against concentration of cobalt, a straight line was obtained for 3 to 50 μg of cobalt(II). The optimum concentration range for the determination of cobalt was 6 to 18 ppm. The Sandell sensitivity was 0.03 ppm, while the practical sensitivity was 0.3 ppm. The molar absorptivity was $2359 \pm 0.6\%$ l. mole⁻¹. cm⁻¹.

Effect of diverse ions : The determination of cobalt(II) was possible in the presence of 37 other metal ions including at least 2 mg of nickel, without using any masking agent. The other metal ions which could be tolerated at least up to 2 mg are zinc(II), manganese(II), magnesium(II), beryllium(II), copper(II), barium(II), mercury(II), cadmium(II), lead(II), calcium(II), tin(II), aluminium(III), chromium(III), bismuth(III), arsenic(III), antimony(III), iridium(III), titanium(IV), vanadium(IV and V), thorium(IV), cerium(IV), molybdenum(VI) and uranium(VI). Osmium(VIII)

could be tolerated up to 1 mg. However, the tolerance limit for iron(III), gallium(III), indium(III), thallium(I), platinum(II), palladium(II), ruthenium(III), rhodium(III), selenium(IV) and zirconium(IV) was up to 100 μg .

Fluoride had to be used to mask copper(II) and iron(III) was reduced to iron(II) with ascorbic acid. The tolerance limit for iron was 100 μg . The tolerance limits of the diverse ions are for error limit of $\pm 2\%$.

Effect of masking agents : The determination of cobalt was feasible in the presence of 1 ml of 0.5% solutions of ascorbic acid, ammonium bifluoride, tartrate, citrate, triethanol amine and phosphoric acid. However, the absorption values were low in the presence of disodium-EDTA or magnesium-EDTA.

Precision and accuracy : The relative standard deviation for 10 determinations of cobalt was $\pm 0.92\%$. The confidence (95%) range was calculated to be 16.21 ± 0.06 ppm.

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